

Rice varieties tested for various deepwater traits.

Variety	Submergence tolerance score ^a	Salt tolerance score ^a	Elongation ability			Elongated internodes (no.)	Kneeing ability
			Final height (cm)	Elongated height (cm) ^b	% of elongation		
TNRI	5	3	119	64	114	2	1
Ponkambi samba	9	3	112	63	129	2	7
Kattuvanam	9	3	111	47	73	2	3
Sarapalli samba	9	5	112	55	95	3	5
Sirumani Amon	9	9	115	56	95	2	3
Deepwater type	9	7	86	17	25	1	3
Donradao	9	7	117	50	75	1	3
Kar paddy	9	3	140	63	82	2	5
Dulai Aman	9	9	106	50	89	1	5
Dulai Baron	9	3	92	26	39	1	7
Dhanya	5	7	115	56	95	3	5
Akulu	9	5	118	52	75	3 ^c	3
Poongar	9	7	84	37	77	3	9
Kala or Black Aman	9	3	93	42	82	1	5
Chingair	9	5	133	65	96	3 ^c	5
Lalkanai	9	9	134	63	89	3	5
Birpak	7	9	140	63	82	4 ^c	1
Lakhi	9	9	110	46	72	3	3
Aeb 368 Rip P type	9	9	95	31	48	1	9
Perunel	9	7	102	39	62	3 ^c	7
White Ottadan	9	9	109	32	42	2	7
Gutak	9	7	77	27	52	2	9
Mahsuri	9	7	111	37	50	2	7
Ponni	9	3	71	30	73	1	7

^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice Scale. ^b Final height minus height before submergence. ^c Presence of nodal roots.

elongated internodes. Chingair, Birpak, Akulu, and Perunel had profuse nodal roots, which increase plant nutrient uptake.

Kneeing ability. Sixty-five-day-old plants were pulled out gently and placed horizontally on the puddled field. Water depth was maintained at 2 cm. Three days

later angle of kneeing was scored (see table). TNRI and Birpak had the most pronounced kneeing.

Photoperiod sensitivity. Seedlings were raised in plastic pots and subjected to photoperiod treatment for 10, 12, 14, and 16 hours. All the varieties treated with 10 and 12 hours photoperiod flow-

ered. Sarapalli samba, Aeb 368 Rip P, and Gutak flowered at the 14 hour treatment, and were considered photoperiod insensitive. (Aeb 368 Rip P did not flower at 16 hours.) All other varieties were photoperiod sensitive and had relatively long basic vegetative phase. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Hybrid rice

Inheritance of polycaryopsis and breeding of polycaryoptic male-sterile rice

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Polycaryoptic rices WX154 (Korea) and Double Rice (Bangladesh), which have more than two ovaries and four stigmas in each floret, were crossed with normal rice varieties 7101 and HR1619-6-2-1,

respectively, and with each other. The F₁ of the crosses of polycaryoptic and normal rices were normal. Segregation in the F₂s agreed with the ratio of three normal to one polycaryoptic. Results

indicate that polycaryopsis in WX154 and Double Rice is each controlled by a single recessive gene. The F₁ of the cross WX154/Double Rice was normal, and the F₂ segregated into nine normal to seven

Segregation for polycaryopsis in the F₂ of the crosses between polycaryoptic WX154^a and normal marker line 7101, polycaryoptic Double Rice^b and normal rice HR1619-6-2-1, and WX154 and Double Rice, IRR.

Cross	F ₁	F ₂ plants (no.)			Ratio	x ²	P
		Normal	Poly-caryoptic	Total			
WX154/7101	Normal	232	68	300	3:1	0.871	.25-.50
HR1619-6-2-1/Double Rice	Normal	139	48	187	3:1	0.045	.50-.90
WX154/Double Rice	Normal	229	158	387	9:7	1.341	.10-.50

^a From Korea. ^b From Bangladesh.

polycaryoptic, indicating that WX154 and Double Rice have duplicate recessive genes for polycaryopsis (see table).

When the polycaryoptic line YA1, a selection from WX154/Tongilchal, was crossed with cytoplasmic male-sterile rice V20A, the F₁ was sterile. The F₁ was backcrossed to YA1. From this BCF₁, polycaryoptic male-sterile plants could be selected (see figure), showing that the polycaryoptic line YA1 is a maintainer for cytoplasmic male-sterility, and that polycaryoptic male-sterile plants selected could be maintained by successive backcrosses to YA1.

Polycaryoptic male-sterile rice may have greater seed set because it has four stigmas instead of two. The possibility of using this male-sterile rice for F₁ hybrid seed production is being explored. □

Polycaryoptic male-sterile (A), polycaryoptic fertile (B), and normal (C) rice.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Effect of abscisic acid on rice seedling resistance to chilling injury

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Rice seedlings Dansheng No. 1, Guichao No. 2, and Shanyou No. 2 were studied for the effects of abscisic acid (ABA) on resistance to chilling injury influenced by hormonal regulation.

ABA accumulation varied with varietal resistance to chilling injury. Five days after the low temperature (8-10°C) treatment, seedlings of cold-resistant Dansheng No. 1 showed an ABA increase over cold-sensitive Shanyou No. 2. The longer the

Change in ABA content in the leaves of Dansheng No. 1 during low temperature.

Days of low temperature	ABA content (ng/g fresh wt)
0	0.65
3	13.50
6	20.60
9	58.50
LSD	0.08

low temperature lasted, the more ABA accumulated in leaves of the seedlings (see table).

Exogenous application of ABA reduced the symptoms of chilling injury such as the leakage of electrolytes from leaves and roots (see figure), leaf discoloration, and reduction of leaf fresh weight. ABA accumulation response should be investigated in further studies. □

Effect of ABA on leakage of electrolytes in chilled rice seedlings.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Sheath rot in the Punjab, India

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Sheath rot (ShR) caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gam. was first reported in India in Hyderabad (A.P.) in 1974 and in Kapurthala (Punjab) in 1980. *Fusarium* has been associated with sheath and panicle rot of rice for the last 3 years,

particularly on variety PR106, but was ignored and considered a secondary invader.

Fusarium symptoms resemble those produced by *S. oryzae*. They are oblong or irregular spots, 5-20 mm long with